

Research on wave defects of tape winding resin matrix composites

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The damage and causes of wave defects of tape winding composites

Resin matrix composites are widely used in all walks of life because of their excellent performances, but it is easy to form defects during the molding processes. Waves are common defects in the tape winding resin matrix composites, and adversely affect mechanical properties of the materials products.

There are four main reasons for the formation of waves in tape winding resin matrix composites:

- ① The shape of fiber tapes deform;
- ② Under the action of temperature and tension, the fiber tapes slip and deform to form waves;
- ③ The vacuum auxiliary materials shrinks after vacuuming to wave the fiber tapes;
- ④ Under the action of pressure during curing process, the liquid resin is squeezed out and pre-formed product shrinks in the radial direction to form wave defects.

Fig.1 Wave defects of tape winding resin matrix composites: (a) composite sample; (b) composite sample without resin; (c) single fiber tape with wave defects.

Effect of curing process on wave defects

Fig.2 The curves of curing degree and temperature with time.

For the resin, the higher curing degree, the lower resin viscosity, and the worse resin fluidity.

Fig.3 Samples cured at different heating rates: (a)15°C/h; (b)20°C/h; (c)25°C/h.

No.	Heating rate /°C/h	Temperatures of pressured point/°C	Density /kg/m ³	Tensile Strength/MPa
1	15	95	1730	43.4~47.0
2		100	1680	42.1~43.4
3		102	1660	40.8~47.2
4		105	1620	33.4~37.5
5	20	102	1680	40.7~46.8
6	25	102	1710	35.9~37.4

Table1 Density and tensile strength of samples with different curing parameters.

Effect of bandage method on wave defects

The vacuum bag with spiral direction fold or tightly wrapped on the surface of product can effectively avoid fiber tape deformation caused by vacuum auxiliary materials

Fig.4 Effect of bandage method on wave defects.